

Khaan Bank Customer Satisfaction of Mongolia

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ABSTRACT

The Mongolian banking sector is one of the most complex and widespread sectors of the economy of Mongolia. As a result of globalization, the world is becoming smaller and business is larger. Due to the growth of technology, customer demand in the banking sector is growing day by day. In this regard, customer satisfaction has become a key aspect of the banking business. The main goal of the study is to find out the level of customer satisfaction with the services offered by Khaan Bank (KB) and to give several possible suggestions for improving the quality of service. This study was based on Ulaanbaatar, the Han Uul sector of the KB. Data were collected from primary and secondary sources. In terms of results, overall customer satisfaction is above average, but not excellent. The bank should emphasize the reputation of customer satisfaction and take further steps to improve the quality of service.

KEYWORDS: customer service, customer satisfaction, service quality, Khaan Bank, Mongolia

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1. INRODUCTION

We live in an era of globalization. Global business competition is escalating. A firm must provide excellent services to distinguish itself from another firm in the market. Customer satisfaction is critical to every business in today's market. This is a way of thinking based on knowledge and past experience. In a competitive world, all organizations pay great attention to their valued customers. The banking sectors are currently the most important bodies in the huge services sector. Commercial banks in Mongolia are one of the key components of the Mongolian economy. Among them, Haan Bank (CB) is a declared own bank, which is registered in accordance with the 1991 Companies Act. Financial institutions believe that all success depends on attractive customer satisfaction. Why financial institutions care more about customer satisfaction, loyalty and retention [1].

Measuring customer satisfaction gives a sense of achievement and fulfillment to all employees involved in any phase of the customer service process. Thus, the measurement of satisfaction motivates people to work and achieve higher levels of productivity[2-4]. Customer satisfaction is seen as a standard performance standard and a possible quality standard for any business organization in a competitive market [5-6].

Satisfied customers always keep in touch with the organization and buy various types of goods and services. The banking sector is growing in Mongolia. Thus, it is difficult for banking sectors to retain customers through the

provision of services. Attractive customer satisfaction is the main source of maintaining a business in a competitive market. Thanks to financial services, such as banking competition in the market with undifferentiated products, this emphasizes service quality as the main competitive tool [7-8].

Customer satisfaction is a mental state in which the results of customer expectations before a purchase are compared with perceptions of performance after a purchase. Satisfied customers are believed to be in contact with the company and buy more goods or services more often than dissatisfied customers.

Customer satisfaction is related to customer loyalty, and customer loyalty is related to bank profitability. Customer satisfaction is an important aspect of serving organizations and is closely related. With quality of service, they are all related to each other; As the quality of service improves, the level of customer satisfaction will also increase, which will lead to more stable relations between the bank and its customers, which will lead to an increase in the level of loyalty and profitability. However, it is almost impossible to keep the whole company constantly motivated by such an abstract and intangible concept as customer satisfaction. Thus, customer satisfaction should be translated into a series of measurable parameters that are directly related to people's work, in other words, factors that people can understand and influence [9-10].

2. Study objectives

The main objective of the study is to study the level of customer satisfaction with the services offered by KB. This study examines various types of factors that affect customer satisfaction in the banking sector. Other objectives of the study are:

- Learn about the deposit scheme KB.
- Examine the impact of online banking on customer satisfaction.
- give some possible suggestions for improving the quality of service.

3. Research methodology

This study is based on primary data. To collect primary data, a questionnaire method is used here, which has 10 questions on this issue. The target group was clients of Ulaanbaatar, Khan-Uul sector in KB. Using a simple random sampling method, 20 clients KB of Ulaanbaatar, Han Uul sector, responded to this. All variables were measured using a 5-point Likert scale, in which the 5 values presented completely correspond to 1, which is a categorical disagreement.

4. Analysis and Results

The main objective of this study is to examine the level of customer satisfaction. Data were collected from primary and secondary sources. The questionnaire is compiled on the basis of some variables that directly or indirectly affect the level of customer satisfaction. Using MS Excel tables, data is analyzed and interpreted. Analysis of the survey data is given below:

Table1. Environment of KB

Frequency		
1	Strongly Disagree	0
2	Disagree	3
3	Neutral	4
4	Agree	6
5	Strongly Agree	7
Total		20

Interpretation:

From the above tables, it can be said that only 7 respondents fully agreed with this fact and 6 agreed. Meanwhile, the number of respondents who strongly disagree with this fact is 0. Here 3 respondents stated that they disagree in this regard, and 4 respondents kept themselves in a neutral direction (see Table-1).

Table2. Employees & Helpful Staffs of KB

Frequency	
Strongly Disagree	0
Disagree	0
Neutral	7
Agree	7
Strongly Agree	6
Total	20

Interpretation:

From the above tables, it can be said that only 6 respondents fully agree with this fact, and 7 agreed. Meanwhile, the number of respondents who strongly disagree and disagree with this paragraph is 0, and 7 respondents kept themselves in an objective direction (see Table-2).

Table3. Relationships with customers of KB

Frequency		
1	Strongly Disagree	0
2	Disagree	2
3	Neutral	6
4	Agree	11
5	Strongly Agree	1
Total		20

Interpretation:

Customer relations are an integral part of any organization. In response to the question, the figure said that 1 respondent fully agrees with the relationship with the client, while 11 respondents agree with this fact. Meanwhile, the number of respondents who expressed a categorical disagreement with this fact is 0. On the other hand, there are 2 respondents who said they disagree with this fact, and 6 respondents kept them neutral (see Table-3).

Table4. Quick Service Delivery of KB

Frequency		
1	Strongly Disagree	0
2	Disagree	3
3	Neutral	5
4	Agree	12
5	Strongly Agree	0
Total		20

Interpretation:

Regarding the quick provision of services to customers, 0 respondents strongly agree with their quick service, 12 respondents agree, 0 respondents strongly disagree with fast service, 3 respondents disagree and 5 respondents are neutral with this fact. Although most customers accept fast delivery, customers are pleased to receive these services (see Table-4).

Table5 KB Offers Best Deposit Schemes

Frequency		
1	Strongly Disagree	1
2	Disagree	4
3	Neutral	13
4	Agree	2
5	Strongly Agree	0
Total		20

Interpretation:

Deposit schemes are the most important level of customer satisfaction. In response to the aforementioned question, not a single respondent completely agreed with this fact, and 2 respondents agreed with this, 1 categorically disagree with this fact. On the other hand, 4 respondents stated that they do not agree with this fact, and 13 respondents are in a neutral position (see Table-5).

Table6. Deposit Money in KB

Frequency		
1	Strongly Disagree	0
2	Disagree	1
3	Neutral	10
4	Agree	5
5	Strongly Agree	4
Total		20

Interpretation:

From the above table and diagram, we can say that only 4 respondents fully agreed with this fact and 5 agreed. Meanwhile, the number of respondents who strongly disagree with this fact is 0. Here, 1 respondent said they did not agree with this, and 10 respondents kept them in a neutral direction (see Table-6).

Conclusion

Despite competition among banks in Mongolia, KB has gained a good reputation around Mongolia. Although there are not enough KBs in many sectors, such as online banking, nonetheless, people are investing in this bank because of its good reputation. This report shows that KB serves its customers and how customers respond to the services they provide. A huge amount of research has been conducted in the banking sector of Mongolia to find out the role of the banking sector in economic development. Banks play an important role in the economies of developing countries such as Mongolia. Therefore, the bank must provide various services to retain customers. In this regard, the bank must determine its strengths and restore weaknesses.

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